

Paulicians

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The Paulicians were a heterodox Christian group which emerged on the eastern frontiers of Byzantine Anatolia and in Armenia in the seventh century, apparently founded by a certain Armenian, Constantine of Samosata, who took the name Silvanus after one of the apostles of Paul, and who, according to legend, converted the official sent to try and execute him for heresy, with this man becoming his successor under the name of Titus, who would himself be executed by burning under Justinian II Rhinometos. Following the immolation of their second leader, and fearing further persecution, the sect fled in a mass exodus to a certain region on the Eastern frontier known as Episparis, and thence to another adjacent region called Mananalis following the trial and acquittal of their leader Gegnaesius for heresy under the auspices of Leo I for fear of further interventions and potential persecution on the part of the Roman state; nevertheless, the emperor Constantine V effected the forced migration of numerous Paulicians to Thrace to strengthen the Thracian frontier, which would be the first of many forced and imperially mandated migrations from Anatolia to the Balkans. The death of Gegnaesius occasioned a schism in the church between the party of Baanes and that of Sergius, with the Sergites gaining the ascendancy apparently proselytizing widely in the eastern provinces, and inviting renewed persecutions under Leo the Armenian. Under Theodora, a still more intense persecution began, which eventually led to the flight of many Paulicians under their leader Karbeas across the border into the districts of Armenia under Islamic rule, where the Emir of Melitene allowed them to construct the fortress city of Tephrike, which acted as a redoubt and buffer state with Byzantium under Arab protection. Nevertheless, in the late 9th century, Basil I conquered these principalities after prolonged wars with a particularly bellicose leader known as Chrysocheir, and while part of the population retreated further into Armenia, merging, evidently, into the emerging Tondrakian movement, much of the rest was deported to the Thracian provinces by he and his immediate successors, where they continued to exist as a distinct ethnoreligious group, renowned as hill raiders and warriors, and concentrated especially in the vicinity of Philippopolis, where they evidently evangelized the local population to their creed. They are believed to be the ancestors of modern day Banat Bulgarians who converted to Catholicism in the 16th and 17th Centuries, as well as of the Muslim Pomaks. It is also possible they had some influence on the Bogomil sect and on that of the Cathars, though this may be a mistaken connection. The basic doctrines of the sect are very much a subject of debate, whether they were dualistic, gnostic, adoptionist, or simply a reformist movement unrelated to these designations. Their Christology seems to have been nontrinitarian, and according to the (admittedly biased) accounts of their belief attributed to the pen of to Petros Sikeliotes, they accepted the New Testament though not the Tanakh, and evidently had iconoclastic tendencies and worshipped in simple meetinghouses, though the account may represent a spurious source. Anna Komnene refers to them as Manichaeans in her *Alexiad*, but this seems to be more an imputation of potential dualism or perhaps a generic term of disparagement rather than any indication that they actually followed the doctrines of Mani. Based on their apparent rejection of imperial ecclesiastical and secular hierarchies, they are sometimes considered an egalitarian or proto-Marxist movement, or, conversely, a proto-protestant one, though such arguments are spurious at best.

Date Range: 650 CE - 1700 CE

Region: Byzantine Empire.

Region tags: Eastern Europe, Byzantium, Dalmatia, Cyprus, Greece, Eastern Mediterranean

The Byzantine Empire, ca 1025.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Garsoïan, Nina G. 1967. *The Paulician Heresy: a Study of the Origin and Development of Paulicianism in Armenia and the Eastern Provinces of the Byzantine Empire* / Nina G. Garsoïan. Reprint 2010. The Hague ; Paris: Mouton & Co.
- Source 2: Seyfeli, Canan. 2020. "Byzantine Paulicians: Beliefs and Practices." *Ulm (Online)* 3 (1): 45-68.
- Source 3: Carl Dixon. 2022. "The Paulicians: Heresy, Persecution, and Warfare on the Byzantine Frontier, 750-880" Leiden: Brill

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Paulicians>
- Source 1 Description: https://medievalchurch.org.uk/h_paul.php

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: N/A

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1100 CE - 1200 CE

Region: Lagoudera

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Paulicians had a potentially adversarial relationships with their Roman Orthodox neighbors.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: No, the Paulicians seems to have believed themselves to be the sole proper interpretation of Christian doctrine

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: There were, also, presumably periods where the Paulicians lived peacefully with their neighbors.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the Paulicians were renowned as soldiers and raiders.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, Paulicians were recruited into the Byzantine army during certain periods and took part in numerous campaigns beyond the boundaries of the empire.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: They seem to actively have sought conversion of non-believers.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The Paulicians practiced baptism by fire.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It would be extremely difficult to estimate this and their population must have varied over time but it must have been sizeable given the threat they posed to central authority and their ability to administer an independent state at Tephrike.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is almost impossible to estimate given the nature of the sources.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (actively discouraged-suppressed by larger religious group(s))

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: The Paulicians seem to have rejected the established church hierarchy in favor of antinomianism.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We do not know enough of the Paulicians attitude to their own religious community to answer this question.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The Paulicians seem to have rejected the Tanakh.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no indication of monumental Paulician architecture and certain sources suggest that their places of worship were modest and unadorned.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Paulician religious practice seems to have been iconoclastic or aniconic in nature though that does not indicate that they had no figurative imagery at all.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably the Paulicians accepted more broadly held Christian doctrines of heaven and hell.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is, to my knowledge, to discernable archaeological record of Paulician funerary practices.

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is, to my knowledge, to discernable archaeological record of Paulician funerary practices.

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is, to my knowledge, to discernable archaeological record of Paulician funerary practices.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: We do not have enough sources to truly access of Paulician perspective on their own religion.

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not enough is known of Paulician doctrine.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not enough is known of Paulician doctrine.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Not enough is known of Paulician doctrine or folk culture.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Food:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of Paulician cultural taboos is not entirely clear from the source material at hand.

Sacred space(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of Paulician cultural taboos is not entirely clear from the source material at hand.

Sacred object(s):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of Paulician cultural taboos is not entirely clear from the source material at hand.

Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of Paulician cultural taboos is not entirely clear from the source material at hand.

Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: One may presume, given the bellicose nature of the Paulicians both in Anatolia and the Balkans, that this was not the case, though is no proof either way.

Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: One may presume, given the bellicose nature of the Paulicians both in Anatolia and the Balkans, that this was not the case, though is no proof either way.

Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The nature of Paulician cultural practices and taboos is not entirely clear from the source material at hand.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: It may be presumed that this is the case given the Christian background of the sect.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: It may be presumed that this is the case given the Christian background of the sect.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: It may be presumed that this is the case given the Christian background of the sect.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: It may be presumed that this is the case given the Christian background of the sect.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician culture is not adequate to answer this question, though it might readily be imagined to be the case in a society of warrior frontiersmen.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician culture is not adequate to answer this question

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: It has been particularly noted that the Paulicians seem to have rejected the ecclesiastical hierarchies of their Orthodox neighbors, which has given rise to historiographies claiming a proto-communist identity for the sect. Though this is far fetched, Paulicianism does seem to have emerged out of and drawn strength from opposition to centralizing and aristocratizing influences.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician culture is not adequate to answer this question

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious and popular culture is not adequate to answer this question

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably the Christology of the Paulicians had a similar sense of messianic time to their neighbors.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Almost certainly yes, but without a Paulician perspective we cannot know what those were or how they were interpreted or enacted in the world.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Contemporary texts indicate that the Paulicians did not practice prohibitions on foods, although these do not originate from practitioners themselves.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at

meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: One may presume that this was the case.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician culture is not adequate to answer this question, though such markers almost certainly existed.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Paulicians emerged within the Byzantine Empire, but came to live in a variety of states of different levels of organization and development. Moreover, their short-lived state of Tephrike represents something of an enigma.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician culture is not adequate to answer this question, but we may presume so.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question, but it would not be unreasonable to presume so.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question, but this is certainly possible.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than

the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We know very little of the structure of the Paulician religious community

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The bureaucracies of the states in which they lived, including Byzantium.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question, though it is possible.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Byzantine Empire as well as other states.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Byzantine courts

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: See executions of Paulician leaders.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: See population transfer and displacement between Anatolia and the Balkans

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Information about Paulician religious culture is not adequate to answer this question

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Roman Law/Armenian and Bulgarian Customary Law

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: Though formidable warriors, it is unclear to what degree their armies were organized or institutionalized.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Presumably similar to the ecclesiastical calendars of neighboring peoples.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Presumably they took part in the traditional transhumant and agricultural ways of life common to Anatolia and the Balkans.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

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